

Trusted Research Environments for Healthcare AI

State of the art global landscape report

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Authors: Ivo Emanuilov, Björn Larsson, Michela Magas, Andrew Dubber

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Executive summary

This global landscape report provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) worldwide, with a particular focus on the Nordic countries and the United Kingdom. TREs—also known as data safe havens—are secure platforms that enable researchers to analyse sensitive data while complying with legal, ethical, and contractual obligations. The report is part of the TRE4HealthAI project, which aims to develop next-generation TRE capabilities tailored for healthcare AI applications.

A key finding of the report is that the **DARE UK Five Safes framework** and the **Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE)** have emerged as the **de facto standard** for TRE implementations in both the UK and across Europe. Originally developed within the UK legal and research context, the Five Safes framework—comprising Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data, and Safe Outputs—has been widely adopted and adapted by TREs internationally. The DARE UK Blueprint, which operationalises this framework, is technology-agnostic and aligns with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), making it suitable for diverse implementations.

In the UK, various research and commercial projects such as the Turing Data Safe Haven, Treehouse, and the Aridhia digital research environment have all been evaluated for conformity with the Five Safes-based SATRE specification. These implementations demonstrate a high degree of standardisation, transparency, and interoperability, setting a benchmark for TRE development.

The report also highlights how European initiatives, particularly the EOSC-ENTRUST project, have mapped their TRE architectures and requirements to the DARE UK Blueprint. TREs in Norway (NORTRE) and Finland (CSC SD) have been shown to align closely with the DARE UK model, despite differences in governance structures—such as the role of data controllers and output approval processes. The EOSC-ENTRUST project has adopted the DARE UK infrastructure layer and extended it to accommodate European legal and organisational contexts.

Furthermore, the report outlines the growing demand for next-generation TRE capabilities, including support for AI model development, federated learning, and scalable cloud infrastructure. These capabilities are being mapped onto the Five Safes framework to ensure continued compliance and security and enable new capabilities for supervisory authorities to learn from the evidence generated in a TRE. Projects like GRAIMATTER and various empirical studies (eg, Kavianpour et al. 2022) provide guidance on integrating AI safely within TREs.

In conclusion, the DARE UK Five Safes framework has become the foundational model for TREs, influencing both national and international implementations. Its adaptability, combined with a strong emphasis on governance and interoperability, positions it as the cornerstone for future TRE development in support of secure, ethical, and innovative research that also enhances evidence-based regulatory learnings.

Introduction

Researchers working with sensitive data must conduct their analysis in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) to meet legal, contractual, and ethical obligations. TREs are also known as data safe havens or secure data environments. Broadly speaking, a TRE refers to various software and hardware configurations combined with integrated information governance processes designed to ensure the security of the data stored within them.

TRE implementations typically include data and analysis tools accessible through a virtual machine with limited internet access. These systems ensure users only have access to the data they need, using a remote desktop connection to connect to the virtual machine.

The TRE4HealthAI project is dedicated to creating a TRE with advanced capabilities for next-generation applications. The project seeks to enable use cases that allow transferability and validation of results from research to production, develop legal, technical, and procedural components that support responsible validation and experimentation within a TRE, and allow for the continuous monitoring of potential drift of data-driven AI applications as they are deployed in clinical environments. These use cases require support for large, unstructured data, parallelisation of computational tasks, software development and access to AI models within the TRE, ability to install software packages freely, and functionality for exporting models to third parties and connecting with external data sources. The use cases will be specified in more details in Deliverable 3: Requirements Specification for Swedish TRE.

These advanced features highlight the project's role in the broader strategy of creating regulatory sandboxes for healthcare applications. By facilitating a secure and controlled environment for prototyping, development and testing, the TRE serves as a foundational platform that aligns with the stringent regulatory standards required for healthcare innovations. We therefore conceptualise a TRE for Healthcare AI as a secure data platform augmented with prototyping, development and testing capabilities that can be embedded into a future regulatory sandbox.

The present document outlines a global view of different applications of TREs across the world, with an emphasis on the Nordics. The objective is to present an overview of reference models and architectures and concrete technical implementations of TREs. This work paves the way for the following steps of comparing the Swedish and Finnish approaches to building TREs and secondary processing of health data and a requirements specification for TRE4HealthAI.

Trusted research environments in the Nordics

A recent study conducted by Lifebit highlighted that Nordic countries, including Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden, have significantly advanced population sequencing and genomics research.¹ Their shared ancestry and homogenous populations simplify the study of disease-related genetic variants and rare genetic conditions. This has driven large-scale population sequencing to support personalised medicine in these countries. National strategies, funding, and collaboration initiatives promote data sharing within the Nordics.²

Norway: NordForsk

An example of the Nordic region's aim to enhance its position in research cooperation and infrastructure was the establishment of **NordForsk** by the Nordic Council of Ministers in 2005. One of NordForsk's initiatives was investing NOK 165 million into research efforts in personalised medicine in collaboration with national funding agencies from Sweden, Iceland, Denmark, Finland, and Norway. The projects funded from this investment focus on the application of personalised medicine in various diseases, including prostate cancer, sleep apnoea, inflammatory bowel disease, ischemic heart disease, severe infectious diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, and the generation of new health economic evidence to inform healthcare decisions.

Advancing precision medicine is a common objective among the Nordic countries, which led to the formation of the Nordic Precision Medicine Initiative (NPMI) and the development of a roadmap for precision medicine in this region.³ These initiatives have promoted collaboration and data sharing between governments, universities, research organisations, and the private sector. However, sharing data requires addressing challenges such as establishing secure infrastructure for storing and sharing information safely. To balance the goals of fostering collaboration and ensuring data security, the Nordics have adopted TREs.⁴

Denmark: the Danish National Genome Centre

The Danish National Genome Centre (DNGC)⁵ is a government agency and authority established in 2019. It was created to implement the Danish Government's National Personalised Medicine Strategy 2017-2020 and 2020-2022.⁶ The DNGC is deploying a fully on-premises TRE and Data Analysis Platform for managing whole genome and clinical data, within the Centre's national supercomputing cluster. In 2022, it announced its partnership with Lifebit aimed at creating a Federated Trusted Research Environment within the centre's supercomputer cluster. This TRE will ensure a scalable and secure data management and

¹ Hadley E. Sheppard, 'Considerations in Establishing Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the Nordics', *Lifebit* (blog), 30 June 2023, <https://www.lifebit.ai/trusted-research-environment/considerations-in-establishing-trusted-research-environments-in-the-nordics>.

² Sheppard.

³ Pål Rasmus Njølstad et al., 'Roadmap for a Precision-Medicine Initiative in the Nordic Region', *Nature Genetics* 51, no. 6 (June 2019): 924–30, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-019-0391-1>.

⁴ Sheppard, 'Considerations in Establishing Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the Nordics'.

⁵ <https://www.eng.ngc.dk/>

⁶ See Danish Ministry of Health, Personalised Medicine for the Benefits of Patients, National Strategy for Personalised Medicine 2017-2020, https://www.eng.ngc.dk/media/6675/sum_klar_diagnose_summary_uk_web.pdf and Danish Ministry of Health, Personalised Medicine for the Benefits of Patients, National Strategy for Personalised Medicine 2021-2022, <https://www.eng.ngc.dk/Media/637614364621421665/Danish%20Strategy%20for%20personalised%20medicine%202021%202022.pdf>

analysis platform for Denmark's national researchers, clinical scientists and international collaborators. The infrastructure is designed to operate in the cloud which should enable international researchers to get secure access to the centre data. In the initial stage of the strategy, the Danish National Genome Centre and its collaborators aim to recruit and sequence the whole genomes of 60,000 patients diagnosed with cancer, autoimmune disorders, and rare diseases.

Finland: the FinnGen project

The FinnGen project is a research project in genomics and personalized medicine. It is large public-private partnership that has collected and analysed genome and health data from 500,000 Finnish biobank donors to understand the genetic basis of diseases. FinnGen is expanding into understanding the progression and biological mechanisms of diseases. FinnGen provides a world-class resource for further breakthroughs in disease prevention, diagnosis, and treatment and a outlook into our genetic make-up.⁷ FinnGen is not a TRE model,⁸ but it is similar in that it is a data environment enabling Finnish universities, hospitals and hospital districts, biobanks, international pharmaceutical companies and Finnish citizens can collaborate and progress precision medicine.

Sweden: Genomic Medicine Sweden

Genomic Medicine Sweden was founded in 2018 and receives funding from the Swedish Innovation Agency, Vinnova, and regional university hospitals and medical faculties, which established a national genomics infrastructure comprising seven regional centres and aims to have sequenced 65,000 samples by 2025. GMS collaborates with the National Genomics Initiative (NGI) platform, which provides access to next generation DNA sequencing, genotyping and associated bioinformatics support.⁹

The Genomic Medicine Sweden's Strategic Plan 2021–2030¹⁰ includes long-term goals of GMS-analysis of complex diseases and integrated omics in clinical routine, the genomics platform integrated in national clinical studies and advanced AI-based interpretation support on the National Genomics Platform. The strategic plan highlighted that “[a] common platform for genomics data is being built as a national, scalable system that will be transferable to other areas and for the benefit of the entire life science ecosystem, thereby strengthening research, development and innovation. This data platform will be designed to be able to utilise healthcare data using powerful AI-based analytical tools.”¹¹

At the end of 2024, Genomic Medicine Sweden (GMS) and the Danish National Genome Centre (DNCGC) renewed their memorandum of understanding (MoU) to advance personalised medicine in Sweden and Denmark. Their collaboration focuses on:

- Exchange of expertise in bioinformatics, secure genomics data storage, and access.
- Addressing legal and ethical considerations regarding data usage.
- Developing health economic models.

⁷ ‘FinnGen: An Expedition into Genomics and Medicine | FinnGen’, accessed 2 March 2025, <https://www.finnngen.fi/en>.

⁸ Sheppard, ‘Considerations in Establishing Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the Nordics’.

⁹ ‘National Genomics Infrastructure (NGI)’, *SciLifeLab* (blog), accessed 2 March 2025, <https://www.scilifelab.se/units/ngi/>.

¹⁰ ‘Genomic Medicine Sweden Strategic Plan 2021-2030’ (Genomic Medicine Sweden, May 2021), <https://genomicmedicine.se/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/GMS-10-year-strategy.pdf>.

¹¹ ‘Genomic Medicine Sweden Strategic Plan 2021-2030’, 2.

- Enhancing participation in EU projects to position the countries as leaders in personalised medicine.
- Promoting patient engagement and professional education.

GMS actively engages internationally through MoUs with initiatives in France and Germany and participation in European efforts such as the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative. With these partnerships, GMS aims to implement precision medicine in clinical settings by leveraging next-generation sequencing for precise diagnosis, treatment, and management of rare diseases, cancer, and infectious diseases.¹²

These Nordic initiatives do not exist in isolation from each other. In the Action plan for Vision 2030, the Nordic Council of Ministers included the goal to enable the secure and frictionless sharing of health data between Nordic countries as one of the priorities.¹³ These initiatives are also situated in the context of an ongoing effort to drive European interoperability and enhance cross-border health data sharing.

Overview of reference architectures and implementations

United Kingdom

SATRE reference architecture

The SATRE project provides a Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (TREs). It incorporates knowledge and best practices from multiple institutions and sectors across the UK. This includes all aspects of TRE provision such as information governance procedures, computing technology, data management and other capabilities.

It aims to standardise the capabilities of TREs, making it easier for users, operators, and developers to work with sensitive data, and making the operation of TREs more transparent to data owners and the general public.

This specification is useful in the cases of (1) a TRE Operator wanting to evaluate or improve their TRE with the suggested capabilities, and (2) a Developer or Builder of new TREs looking for guidance in their thinking and decision making.

Turing Data Safe Haven

The Turing Data Safe Haven is an open source framework for creating secure environments to analyse sensitive data. It provides a set of scripts and templates that will allow you to deploy, administer and use your own secure environment. It was developed as part of the Alan Turing

¹² ‘Genomic Medicine Sweden and the Danish National Genome Center Strengthen Collaboration in Personalised Medicine | Genomic Medicine Sweden’, accessed 2 March 2025, <https://genomicmedicine.se/en/2024/12/19/gms-and-danish-national-genome-center-strengthen-collaboration-in-precision-medicine/>.

¹³ Nordic Council of Ministers, ‘Action Plan for Vision 2030’, 14 December 2020, <https://www.norden.org/en/information/action-plan-vision-2030>.

Institute's Data Safe Havens in the Cloud project.¹⁴ The project was evaluated for conformity with the SATRE reference architecture.¹⁵

DARE UK Sprint Project: Trusted Research Environment and Enclave for Hosting Open Original Science Exploration

TREEHOOSE is an open-source platform for deploying TREs on Amazon Web Services (AWS). It includes open-source tooling to streamline building and operating TREs on public cloud infrastructure whilst maintaining security and trust. The recent Goldacre Review ("Better, Broader, Safer: Using Health Data for Research and Analysis") highlighted the need for standardisation across TREs, ideally through the use of open-source infrastructure.

TREEHOOSE is under active development. It is suitable for anyone interested in deploying a trusted research environment on AWS. Currently it has good support for launching customised Windows Desktops, and limited support for Linux workspaces with SSH access. All access is managed through a TRE web interface which prevents unauthorised egress of confidential data. Features include automated backups for researcher workspaces, secure egress requiring approvals from data governors or other authorised personnel, and budget alerts to help manage spending.¹⁶ The project was evaluated for conformity with the SATRE reference architecture.¹⁷

Aridhia Digital Research Environments

The Aridhia DRE is changing the way in which clinical and research professionals work together; enabling them to collaborate, access and share secure data in a trusted research environment to deliver better patient outcomes.¹⁸ The project was evaluated for conformity with the SATRE reference architecture.¹⁹

Guidelines and Resources for Artificial Intelligence Model Access from Trusted Research Environments

TREs have historically only supported traditional data analysis. There is an increasing need to also facilitate training of AI/ML models within TREs as well as the need to export them from the TREs for use by other researchers. The Guidelines and Resources for Artificial Intelligence Model Access from Trusted Research Environments (GRAIMATTER)²⁰ project formulates key points of the recommendations for disclosure control of trained machine learning (ML) models from TREs are:

1. **Risk assessment.** Develop and apply tests to assess the risk of re-identification from ML models, with expert interpretation required for accurate risk assessment.
2. **Safer models.** Suggest ways to make ML models safer, such as omitting certain values or using techniques like differential privacy to protect data by design.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/data-safe-haven>

¹⁵ https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/evaluations/alan_turing_institute.html#evaluation-alan-turing-institute

¹⁶ HicResearch/TREEHOOSE: DARE UK Sprint Project: Trusted Research Environment and Enclave for Hosting Open Original Science Exploration

¹⁷ Health Informatics Centre Trusted Research Environment (HIC-TRE), University of Dundee — Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments 0.0 documentation

¹⁸ Aridhia DRE | Aridhia DRE: The next-generation Trusted Research Environment

¹⁹ Paper – Assessing the Aridhia DRE Against the SATRE Specification | Trusted data sharing and collaborative data science.

²⁰ GRAIMATTER: Guidelines and Resources for Artificial Intelligence Model Access from Trusted Research Environments - DARE UK

3. **Inherent safety.** Explore methods to build ML models inherently safe, including the use of 'safe wrappers' in the code to ensure privacy.
4. **Release mechanisms.** Consider whether the ML model needs to be released at all or if it can be accessed through a query server to prevent direct access and reduce attack risks.
5. **Ethical and legal considerations.** Address the complex ethical approval process for ML models, considering their potential uses and transfer to other parties, and ensure that the release mechanism aligns with ethical approvals.
6. **Training and costs.** Highlight the need for training for ethical committees, researchers, and TRE staff, and acknowledge the higher costs associated with output checking for ML models compared to traditional analyses.
7. **Public engagement.** Engage with the public to understand their views on acceptable risk levels and balance privacy risks with public benefits.

The project found that safe thresholds for ML models vary based on the dataset and model type, requiring expert interpretation and multiple tests to determine safety. Tests have already been developed which can be used by TRE operators to assess ML model safety. Techniques like differential privacy and 'safe wrappers' can help build safer ML models, but they don't guarantee complete safety, so tests are still necessary. It is possible to measure the riskiness of ML models and develop safer practices, but expert input is needed for disclosure checking. No strict recommendations are made for control measures; TREs should find the best combination of checks and controls for their needs.²¹

Europe

EOSC-ENTRUST is a research project which aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.²²

EOSC-ENTRUST has produced a draft roadmap for the EOSC-ENTRUST common blueprint for federated data access and analysis, also known as the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. The complete blueprint should include template legal agreements, architecture specifications, operating procedures, interface definitions, and a glossary of terminologies.

The Roadmap has three phases:

- **Phase 1 (2024):** Identify Blueprint requirements and match them to existing TRE capabilities.
- **Phase 2 (2025):** Develop and validate key components of the Blueprint.

²¹ Ritchie et al., 'Machine Learning Models in Trusted Research Environments -- Understanding Operational Risks'.

²² 'European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) Project', EOSC-ENTRUST, accessed 2 March 2025, <https://eosc-entrust.eu/about>.

- **Phase 3 (2026):** Release the final Blueprint.

The project will also produce training materials for the Blueprint and a TRE Provider Catalogue detailing interoperability capabilities. Updated versions of these items will be released every November.

To ensure alignment with use cases and TRE providers, yearly workshops will be held in May (focused on requirements and capabilities) and September (focused on evaluation and adoption). According to the original schedule, the Roadmap is expected to be revised in May 2025 and May 2026 based on workshop outcomes.²³

The project adopted the following metamodel for capturing the strategic and business levels of secure processing environments and their technical and organisational measures. While strategic level items are not directly related to the business level, they affect business level decisions:

Figure 1 EOSC-ENTRUST Metamodel

EOSC-ENTRUST has four drivers, or use cases, which are prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities. Each driver highlights and validates specific aspects of the TRE functionality and represents different sectors (eg, health, social sciences, public/private collaborations) which require secure and reliable sharing and analysing of sensitive data.²⁴

²³ Sætrom et al., Deliverable D13.1. Draft Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. 31st May 2024, 4.

²⁴ 'European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) Project', EOSC-ENTRUST, accessed 2 March 2025, <https://eosc-entrust.eu/drivers>.

Driver	Challenge	Driver approach	Expected impact
<p>Driver 1: Federated human genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision</p>	<p>Genetic data generated in a healthcare context is subject to more stringent information governance than research data and must adhere to national data regulations and laws. Using TREs is an accepted model for enabling secondary reuse of this data for research and is suitable for very large volumes of data. Within the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) and the Federated EGA (FEGA) projects, over twenty countries or nodes across Europe will be launching TREs for genomics data.</p> <p>Genomic data is considered a special category of personal data by GDPR and, hence, never anonymous. Real-world examples are lacking about using cross border TREs that include the ethical and legal aspects, together with the technical aspects of pseudonymity and anonymity by aggregation. TRE services for genetic data, which can be reused for other data types at volume, will</p>	<p>This driver will reuse analysis workflows deposited at WorkflowHub, to process data served by FEGA members using Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) and other established standards. The development and testing phases would use synthetic, non-sensitive, data and would further be validated with sensitive data. The driver partners (BSC, CRG, CSC, EMBL-EBI) have extensive experience of sharing human genetic data and manage the federated model for discovery and access via FEGA which forms a core supporting infrastructure for the GDI.</p> <p>The partners are leaders in the development and implementation of global standards for discovery and access of genomic data via the GA4GH. The driver partners (including many of the core project partners through ELIXIR) will take the baseline legal, operational and technical developments of the</p>	<p>The GDI nodes are provided with a working use case about how to become federated TRE providers that involves all legal, ethical and technical considerations. Technical solutions for managing data at a volume, leveraging existing standards would be provided. The federation of TREs is easily extended to nodes as they develop the infrastructure capabilities.</p>

	<p>require the connection of HPC resources.</p>	<p>Federated EGA, and use them as input to the EOSC-ENTRUST architecture. Developments from EOSC-ENTRUST will be fed back to the GDI, to balance the domain-specific needs with interdisciplinary, EOSC-based standards</p>	
<p>Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative/register and social science data</p>	<p>In many countries, data sharing in the social sciences is carried out in national data centres of excellence with mature TREs. Those TREs develop standards for interoperability to enable collaborative work using multiple TRE capabilities. However, these efforts face obstacles such as:</p> <p>(1) Common terminology - many countries have developed their own administrative and social science database environments, which reflect the characteristics of data management in that country. To make these different approaches comparable, a set of definitions should be established</p> <p>(2) Legislative and governance challenges - harmonisation of the</p>	<p>CESSDA and affiliated national entities will provide their TRE capabilities and expertise to inform specifications (legal, operational and technical) and to identify and promote common standards to enable sensitive data sharing. A solid foundation has been laid by past and present trans-national projects, e.g. the Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud (WP5 of SSHOC), the International Data Access Network (IDAN) and the International Secure Data Access Facilities Professionals Network (ISDFPN).</p> <p>Collectively, these projects developed a framework for implementing trans-national data sharing agreements and enabled new remote access connections. The aim is now to expand and test</p>	<p>CESSDA as an organisation will provide greater interoperability in social science resources, allowing collaborative projects at an international scale and at cross-domain level. The International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network (ISDFPN), set up under SSHOC and now jointly run by the UK Data Service and GESIS, will provide improved expert and sustainable support for data professionals working in TREs by providing additional resource.</p>

	<p>differences arising from the legal environment and the conditions of use allowed by the data owner and regulations set by the institutional systems of public and private organisations.</p>	<p>the framework with a new secure data service and look at how it can be extended to cross-domain data sharing and the sharing of novel forms of data, such as digital behavioural data or qualitative data.</p>	
<p>Driver 3: Enabling secure transnational reuse of clinical research data in a legally and ethically compliant manner</p>	<p>Clinical research data sharing and reuse is increasingly regarded as a key requirement for accelerating scientific discoveries and improving healthcare provision. When the scientific community has access to Individual Participant Data (IPD) that underlie research results, new analyses can be performed by other researchers with different ideas, and expertise and data can be pooled for meta-analysis to increase statistical power. Besides the IPD, other clinical research data sources should be made available for sharing (e.g., research protocols, clinical study reports, statistical analysis plans) to enable a full understanding of any dataset.</p> <p>Despite a “call for action” from major stakeholders, the</p>	<p>To address this challenge, the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) has partnered with the University of Oslo to design and operate a TRE adapted to the specific needs of the clinical research community, building upon TSD, a sensitive data infrastructure in Norway, and ensuring compliance with European regulations and the GDPR. Driver 3 will provide the EOSC ENTRUST TRE network with minimum requirements (ethical, legal, organisational, semantic and technical) for clinical research data. The current model developed by ECRIN and TSD will be validated against the TRE blueprint and align its policies and procedures according to the outputs of WPs 5-6 to enhance interoperability among different TREs for clinical research.</p>	<p>The adoption of the EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint by TREs will provide the necessary requirements (ethical, legal, organisational, semantic and technical) to enable clinical research data sharing and re-use in a secure and legally and ethically compliant manner through the development of a common federated model sharing common workflows. In addition to improving the conditions and levels of clinical research data sharing, the involvement of HDR UK will enable demonstration of feasibility in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using routine health data for supporting the planning and performance of data-enabled clinical trials. • Developing predictive models and increasing knowledge

	<p>percentage of clinical research studies that make their IPD and associated files available for re-use is low, due to, among others, ethical, legal, organisational, semantic and technical barriers. In view of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the secondary use of routinely collected health data for research purposes is increasingly gaining momentum in Europe and several national health data hubs are developed. Moreover, routinely collected health data (e.g., electronic health records, medical claims) is a vast data source that has the potential to inform the design and conduct of clinical research, especially with regards to patient recruitment, stratification, and outcome assessment.</p>	<p>EOSC-ENTRUST will provide input on the generation of a data quality stamp and the extension of the analytical tools within the TRE used by ECRIN and the University of Oslo. HDR UK will contribute to develop recommendations around minimum requirements for further interoperability with their routinely collected health data. There will also be an opportunity to explore use cases around the use of research data linked to routinely collected data and explore data governance and access solutions to enable use of linked data.</p>	<p>about diagnosis, treatment and outcome by combining routine health data, observational studies and clinical trial data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting systematic/scoping reviews and development of policy measures by combining different data types (routine health data, clinical trials, observational studies, cohorts, registers). <p>All material and resources produced through this work will be openly shared to inform policy and requirements to improve use of data for clinical research in a trustworthy manner.</p>
<p>Driver 4: Public-private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data</p>	<p>Digital transformation has swept through industry and huge amounts of data requiring protection are currently gathered by companies and SMEs (e.g. through wearables). For instance, the wellbeing industry can collect data on their customers' health, sport activities and daily habits, and smart cities studies can be</p>	<p>Driver 4 will focus on research and innovation projects led by higher education and research institutions that processes data from their partners in the private sectors. Driver partners (Turku UAS, CSC and Sigma2) will elaborate a set of requirements for a technical platform that can support research institutions and</p>	<p>The EOSC-ENTRUST approach will be shown to work with private sector data. Input for blueprint and technology development will be provided from the viewpoint of public-private research collaborations, facilitating the use of valuable privately collected data related to research and innovation projects.</p>

	<p>used by construction companies and research institutions to design optimal housing solutions on the basis of individuals' data and habits.</p> <p>These data are of interest to customers and companies, but also for advancing research and improving national wellbeing. However, practices, protocols, and digital solutions to enable use of data requiring protection (to comply with GDPR regulations, national privacy protecting legislation and business confidentiality) in the private sector are often lacking. In addition, efficient collaboration between private sector and research institutions requires secure digital workspaces and shared data management best practice.</p>	<p>organisations from the private sector to securely and jointly process data requiring protection (either for business confidentiality or GDPR and other privacy protection regulations). Their existing sensitive data services will be tested against the identified requirements to find the optimal blueprint allowing the management of data between public research and private sector while still ensuring protection and security.</p> <p>In this driver, Turku UAS will lead the requirements gathering from the community among their collaboration network and provide the test data sets and research questions for data analysis. If required, Driver 4 will modify the TRE at partner CSC for the requirements of the public-private research project. Sigma2 will evaluate the proof-of-concept solution and its applicability from a national needs perspective. Turku UAS will validate the applicability of the results for their research network.</p>	<p>Applicability of the blueprint for the use in public cloud environments will be considered. By contributing to the development of policy briefings and outreach (WP2) the driver will facilitate wider adoption of the blueprint at SMEs and smaller research institutions enabling a growing ecosystem.</p>
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In December 2024, the project published the first (year one) version of the blueprint.²⁵ In the document, the authors highlight that “existing specifications and implementations of sensitive data processing environments are based on stand-alone design with no or very limited data interoperability.”²⁶ Their focus is therefore on providing a vision of interoperability which is based on the preliminary versions of the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint.

The DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint is based on the Five States framework (discussed below) and dataspace design thinking to allow research on sensitive data within a network of participating TREs. This blueprint describes an architecture based on the idea of conducting secure research on sensitive data residing with different sensitive data providers. It therefore includes services for linking sensitive data, services for secure data analysis (incl. federated analysis), and services for running the secure network itself. The blueprint is technology-agnostic and consists of:²⁷

- **Infrastructure layer**, which describes the federation participants and how data and information flows between these.
- **Data layer**, which uses the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to frame minimal requirements regarding metadata about the federation and about the data within the federation, and
- **Organisational layer**, which outlines requirements for a federation authority and discusses pros and cons of centralised vs distributed organisational models for a federation authority.

The DARE UK Blueprint data space model depicts how sensitive data providers participate in a federation. The data space model supports four data usage patterns: **Q0** (data from one dataset within a single region), **Q1** (same type of data from multiple regions), **Q2** (different data types from individuals within the same region), and **Q3** (multiple data types from multiple regions).²⁸ Working under the assumption that future analysis of sensitive research data will be performed within a TRE, the DARE UK Blueprint describes the minimal capabilities to support these analysis patterns. It describes capabilities needed to link individual-level datasets between different data providers (Q2, Q3) and run federated analyses across geographically distinct data providers (Q1, Q3).

²⁵ Pål Sætrum et al., ‘EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year One Version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework’, 10 December 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>.

²⁶ Sætrum et al., 5.

²⁷ For more details on each of these layers, see Sætrum et al., 10–14.

²⁸ Sætrum et al., 10.

Figure 2 DARE UK conceptual data space²⁹

In addition to the data space model, the DARE UK Blueprint Infrastructure Layer is designed to support secure research on sensitive data within a network of participating TREs. There are no specific requirements regarding the implementation, but the blueprint assumes that participating TREs follow commonly agreed minimal standards, such as SATRE or ISO 27001. The infrastructure layer includes the following components:

1. Participants and actors

- **Participants** include Federation Services, TREs, Software Services, Index Services, Discovery Services, and Job Submission Services.
- **Actors** include Researchers, Data Controllers, and TRE Governance.

2. TRE capabilities

- **Research analytics zones (RAZs)** which provide researchers access to sensitive data for analysis.
- **Secure data zones (SDZs)** which support data management functions such as data set linkage.
- **Query management zones (QMZs)** which facilitate data set discovery and federated analyses.

3. Federation services

- **Accounting, Management, Monitoring, Registry, and Trust Services** which coordinate functions defining the federation, including recording participants, data sets, approved projects, and users.

4. Security server interface which ensures secure data and information flow between participants and actors.

The DARE UK Blueprint assigns the following roles and allocates the following responsibilities:

- **Researchers** who can access data as Project Members within RAZs.

²⁹ Sætrum et al., 11.

- **Data controllers** who are legally responsible for data sets, releasing data for authorised research projects.
- **TRE governance** which includes a team of people running the TRE with roles like TRE operator, Data manager, Output approver, and Job approver, depending on the TRE's capabilities.

The infrastructure layer ensures minimal required functionality for secure data linkage and federated analyses, maintaining the Five Safes principles for sensitive data research.

Figure 3 Minimal required functionality, actors, and role in the DARE UK Blueprint infrastructure layer

TRE provider mapping

The EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint mapped the ENTRUST TRE providers to the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint. These providers include NORTRE, SURF SANE, and CSC SD. For the sake of brevity and in light of the project's focus, we only focus on NORTRE and CSC SD.

Norwegian Trusted Research Environments (NORTRE)

The **Norwegian Trusted Research Environments (NORTRE)** is a collaboration between three main institutional research infrastructures for sensitive data in Norway. These infrastructures are TSD³⁰ (services for sensitive data) at University of Oslo, HUNT Cloud³¹ at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, and SAFE³² (secure access to research data and e-infrastructure) at University of Bergen. Technical details of these infrastructures are provided in the section on architecture. These infrastructures share knowledge and expertise so scientists and data controllers from Norway and around the world can collect, analyse, store, share and collaborate on sensitive data in an optimised and trustworthy manner.³³

³⁰ 'Services for Sensitive Data (TSD) - University of Oslo', accessed 2 March 2025, <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/index.html>.

³¹ 'HUNT Cloud', accessed 2 March 2025, <https://about.hdc.ntnu.no/>.

³² 'SAFE', University of Bergen, accessed 2 March 2025, <https://www.uib.no/en/foremployees/131011/safe>.

³³ 'NORTRE', accessed 2 March 2025, <https://nortre.no/>.

The data holders in NORTRE do not have their own TREs associated with them. The research institutions are instead data controllers while the NORTRE partners are data processors. Reportedly, NORTRE supports the Norwegian health authorities to develop European Health Data Space-ready secure processing environments (SPEs) for transferring data from the national health data access body to these environments.³⁴

The NORTRE partners TSD and SAFE have demonstrated a federation between their services which allows transfer of data through the TSD API.

Figure 4 Federation between NORTRE TSD and SAFE

Finnish Trusted Research Environment

CSC – IT Centre for Science operates as Finland’s national research service provider with a role limited to that of data processor. Its costs are fully covered by contracts with ministries according to its statutes.³⁵ The services are deployed in three use cases, ie, academic use, secondary use of health data under national authority of Findata, and secondary use of health data under a single register holder.

The primary use of research data involves researchers having full control of the sensitive data they intend to process. In the case of personal data, this typically means working with social, health, or genetic data obtained on the basis of explicit consent.³⁶

The Finnish Secondary Use of Health Data Act, enacted in 2019, complicated the secondary use of health data under Findata’s authority. This act designated Findata as the coordinator and manager of social and health registry data use. Users require an explicit permit to process data within a secure environment. To meet these conditions, CSC must manually establish the project for permit holders and transfer the dataset from Findata, thereby creating the TRE Data

³⁴ Sætrum et al., ‘EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year One Version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework’, 14–15.

³⁵ Sætrum et al., 28.

³⁶ Sætrum et al., 29.

Management Zone. Once users access their environment, they can only import data using the system clipboard.

In cases where access is requested to data sets available from one health data controller, it is permissible to manage the process without Findata's involvement. An example is when a medical student needs to work on clinical thesis data under the supervision of a senior adviser. In this case, the advisor would be the data controller using the automated secondary use data management service to deposit the data and make it available to the student only the access control service. The data set is not made publicly available, which also reduces the need to include detailed, formal metadata.

In summary, the mapping exercise found that most features and components presented in the DARE-UK architecture blueprint can be found also among these EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Providers that were mapped to it, with the exception of the Federation service.³⁷

Driver requirements mapping

The EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint also mapped ENTRUST Driver requirements to the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint. It analysed each Driver's user journey and requirements against the DARE UK Blueprint, focusing on mapping the Driver's data usage patterns against the DARE UK Data Space Model and on mapping requirements missing from the SATRE framework or other requirements related to interoperability against the capabilities in the DARE UK Blueprint infrastructure layer.³⁸

Driver 1 ensures secure management and cross-border sharing of sensitive genomics data for research. It provides an infrastructure that makes datasets FAIR while allowing each Data Controller to maintain control over its reuse. Relevant usage patterns for Driver 1 include dataset reuse, meta-analyses between datasets, combining genomics data sets with personal data from other sources (eg, health data or population-based studies). The latter requires data controllers to facilitate linking with other data since individual-level data are normally stored with data set-specific pseudonymised IDs.³⁹ This means that approving and facilitating data set reuse with other sources falls on each data set's data controller, which makes research involving the combination of data sets challenging.

The user journey for Driver 1 includes the activities of data discovery, access application, data access and analysis, export of results, and compliance and reporting. Key requirements for this use case include:

- Anonymisation (in the form of guidelines for techniques to protect individual privacy across all participating institutions)
- Internet connection from within the TRE
- Scalable infrastructure

Driver 2 facilitates easy sharing of sensitive administrative and social science data across borders. The analysis of geographically distinct data sets is the main focus together with

³⁷ Sætrom et al., 34.

³⁸ Sætrom et al., 37.

³⁹ Sætrom et al., 37.

combined analysis with other data, eg, integration with health records or questionnaires, data transfer of digital behavioural data sets, and linking anonymised surveys with sensitive data.⁴⁰

The user journey for Driver 2 includes data discovery, project application, user certification, data access and analysis, and handling output requests. Key requirements for this case include:

- Data transfer between environments
- Compliance with national legal frameworks for data sharing
- Mechanisms for timely deletion of data post-expiration
- Safe researchers training and certification
- Creation and dissemination of general training modules
- Data citation

Driver 3 aims to overcome challenges in sharing and reusing data within the clinical research community, incl. data set reuse, meta-analyses between different clinical trials data sets, and combining clinical trial data with health care data from the same individual.⁴¹

The user journey for Driver 3 includes data discovery, project application, user training in information governance, data access and analysis, handling output requests, and publishing with data credit attribution. Key requirements for this use case include:

- Data encryption for data in transit
- Software applications
- Archiving for reproducibility or future validation
- Basic training in using the TRE's project space
- Data kept only within the agreed time period
- Credit attribution to the original data generator
- Data set discovery
- Metadata
- Data standardisation and data anonymisation

Driver 4 covers collaborative data processing between higher education and research institutions and private sector entities. Key aspects include data analysis combining data sets that are geographically distinct or form different domains (eg, combining health records with data from health technologies, eg, wearable devices).

The user journey for Driver 4 covers the process of setting up a collaborative project within the specific TRE implementation. Key requirements for this use case include:

- Service design
- Ethical guidance
- Backup

⁴⁰ Sætrum et al., 38.

⁴¹ Sætrum et al., 39.

Architecture specifications

The mapping of the selected providers and drivers to the DARE UK Blueprint conducted by the EOSC-ENTRUST project found that the DARE UK Blueprint largely aligns with existing Provider capabilities and supports many Driver requirements.⁴²

Figure 5 ENTRUST infrastructure architecture

Three out of four Drivers have identified Safe User training and certification as essential requirements for federation services. While established specifications or standards for individual TREs, such as SATRE, encompass user training and certification, a federated network of TREs necessitates an agreed-upon minimal common training and a uniform process for user certification.

Specifically, only certified Researchers should be designated as Project Members and granted access to Project environments. The architecture incorporates a Train User process as part of Federation Services. Given that certification is closely linked with user authentication and authorisation, the architecture also integrates the Certify User process within a dedicated Authentication, Authorisation, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI) capability within Federation Services.

The authors of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint recommend that the architecture should also include a process for revoking user certification is also necessary, eg, if a user is found to be violating ethical standards for sensitive data research. The first version of the ENTRUST Blueprint does not include this feature. They also highlight that the Federation Services could be extended to include a registry of national and regional legislation and regulations for participating TREs, providing a framework for compliance with legal frameworks and regulations.

Two of the four Drivers identified general user training, including basic TRE project space training, as essential. The architecture includes “Train user” as a required process for a TRE, in addition to

⁴² Sætrum et al., 43.

the Federation Services' Train user process. TRE training is modelled separately from federation training to accommodate different project environment implementations for TRE participants.

Three providers, SAFE, TSD, and CSC SD Services, identified a gap in the RAZ architecture. Their architectures require the PI (Project Researcher) to be both the Output Approver and Input Approver for the Project's environment. These roles are included in the ENTRUST RAZ model.

For TREs that provide Remote Access Zones (RAZ) and do not act as data controllers, the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint authors list three primary reasons why the Principal Investigator (PI) should be the Output Approver instead of TRE Governance:⁴³

- Data controller or its representative authorises access to their data for specific research projects, which must include the individuals permitted to access the data. The most secure approach is to restrict this list to the project's researchers and exclude TRE Governance. Otherwise, TRE Governance would need to be named in the permit or legally represent the original data controller.
- Assigning the Output Approver role to TRE Governance when the TRE is not the data controller creates a significant bottleneck that could hinder infrastructure scalability.
- Such an assignment raises questions regarding the legal responsibilities of the TRE versus those of the project PI.

This understanding is based on the assumption that RAZ are comparable with the EHDS Secure Processing Environments under the European Health Data Space Regulation.

Three of four Drivers identified handling data access requests as essential, while two Drivers saw functions related to making data FAIR—standardising and publishing—as critical. These specialised optional Secure Data Zones (SDZ) functions are included in a Secure Data Archive (SDA). SDAs can be general or discipline-specific sensitive data archives, like the Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive (FEGA). In the EOSC-ENTRUST modified architecture, SDAs store and provide Curated Data, which may include datasets from published studies or ongoing curation by Data Custodians. Curated Data should have unique IDs and metadata for credit attribution. Though general SDZs can store sensitive data during management or curation, curated data for research should be stored in an SDA.⁴⁴

Two of the four Drivers identified anonymisation functions as essential requirements. As noted in the mapping, the Drivers may instead require specific pseudonymisation services to enable data reuse involving individual-level merging of datasets. Specifically, for any given dataset of Curated Data with pseudonymised project-specific IDs, the linkage spine that maps the project-specific IDs to directly identifiable IDs must be available for future reference in an Index Service. It is important to note that the linkage spine constitutes sensitive data and should only be provided for approved linkage requests.⁴⁵

Given that each Index Service maintains its own registry of linkage spines and allows for overlap queries, a federation consisting of one or more Index Services can facilitate Dataset linkage and assist in answering Discovery Service queries related to overlaps between data stored at different Secure Data Zones within the federation. Notably, with Project, Dataset, and Linkage spine

⁴³ Sætrom et al., 45.

⁴⁴ Sætrom et al., 46–47.

⁴⁵ Sætrom et al., 47–48.

registries, it is not necessary to link actual data to respond to such overlap queries. Consequently, an Index Service has been included in the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint with a Pseudonymisation service that produces and stores project-specific Linkage spines in its own Linkage spines registry. This Pseudonymisation process should be employed as part of the procedure for making project-specific data available in Project environments.⁴⁶

Alignment with the Five Safes framework

The DARE UK Blueprint uses the Five Safes framework to enable research on sensitive data within a network of participating TREs. It is technology agnostic, supporting diverse TRE implementations, and aligns with the FAIR research principles of being as open as possible and as closed as necessary. Although it aligns well with the ENTRUST Blueprint and most existing deployments of TREs, it was developed within the UK legal context for sensitive data research. Therefore, mapping ENTRUST TREs to the DARE UK Blueprint aimed to assess how well the DARE UK Blueprint could support existing TRE architectures across Europe.

The EOSC-ENTRUST project focuses on four TREs from three countries (Norway, Finland, Netherlands) instead of involving all ENTRUST Providers. The difference between the three analysed TREs and the DARE UK Blueprint lies in **who (ie, which actor) approves output from Project environments**, which likely reflects legal or organisational differences between UK TREs and the Norwegian and Finnish TREs. Many UK TREs hold their own data (ie, the TRE is the Data Controller of data requested for output approval); in the Finnish and Norwegian TREs, the data owner often is a separate organisation and output control is the responsibility of the PI of the project with permission to analyse the data. This practice is well established for research projects, but the authors of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint note that the ongoing work in the EHDS on secondary use of health data may introduce other constraints. We have provided an updated version of the DARE UK infrastructure layer that allows for the Norwegian and Finnish architectures.⁴⁷

The mapping of Driver requirements focused on requirements missing from the SATRE framework or other requirements related to interoperability. Most of the Driver requirements mapped directly to capabilities in the DARE UK Blueprint, but we found five requirements to be missing corresponding capabilities in the DARE UK Blueprint. Notably, each of these requirements were listed by at least two Drivers. We note that capabilities for supporting some of these requirements, such as safe user training and certification and general user training have been defined as out of scope for the DARE UK Blueprint. Other requirements, such as data access requests and pseudonymisation may be implicitly supported by other more general capabilities in the DARE UK Blueprint. However, we have chosen to suggest an ENTRUST version based on the DARE UK infrastructure layer where capabilities supporting essential requirements are explicitly modelled.⁴⁸

⁴⁶ Sætrom et al., 47–48.

⁴⁷ Sætrom et al., 48.

⁴⁸ Sætrom et al., 48.

Next-generation capabilities for TREs

AI models access from TREs

In a study conducted in 2022, a team of researchers contacted 73 TRE operators, 22 (30%) of whom, in the United Kingdom and internationally, and conducted interviews under a nondisclosure agreement about their TREs.⁴⁹

The findings from this study show that next-generation TRE capabilities should include:

- Support for big, nonstructured data (such as genomic and imaging data, which can be several terabytes in size)
- Ability to parallelize computational jobs to either a high-performance computing cluster or a graphics processing unit (GPU) farm
- Support for software development within the TRE
- Freedom to install software packages of researcher choice
- Ability to export software and AI algorithms from the environment
- Ability to connect to certain internet locations, for example, code repositories (GitHub)

The interviewees discussed the next-generation capabilities in the context of the different ‘safe’ principles of TREs.

Mapping next-generation capabilities onto the Five Safes framework

In terms of **Safe Data**, they pointed to the need for affordable tools that can be used in TREs to support deidentification of data and assess the risk of reidentification; in particular, building on the existing use of the free sdcMicro toolkit should be considered. Data identifiability is not binary, and data can be identified indirectly by combining attributes, which is known as a triangulation attack.⁵⁰

Regarding the principles of **Safe Outputs**, the study highlights that developing AI models in TREs without compromising patient privacy requires tools to quantify their risk and vulnerability to attacks (eg, membership inference attacks, deanonymisation attacks, reconstruction attacks, model extraction attacks, and model inversion attacks) and consider integrating privacy mechanisms in the model development to counter these attacks. Best practice guidelines can also help users to design robust and safe algorithms, including through auditable and explainable AI. Software tools to check for nonmalicious export by comparing individual data within the TRE with those in the export files is a possibility, but such tools are not currently routinely used by any of the TREs. Barriers to their use by TREs include the attack-specific nature of such tools and their high price. For software development (as opposed to AI models, where the training data are essential input for the end product), exporting the software from the TRE can be avoided entirely by developing it outside.⁵¹

⁴⁹ Sanaz Kavianpour et al., ‘Next-Generation Capabilities in Trusted Research Environments: Interview Study’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 24, no. 9 (20 September 2022): e33720, <https://doi.org/10.2196/33720>.

⁵⁰ Kavianpour et al., 3–4.

⁵¹ Kavianpour et al., 5.

A hybrid model with automated checks can facilitate and accelerate export and reduce the risk of reidentification, checking more thoroughly for inadvertent and malicious inclusion of data. Best practice guidance regarding methods to reduce the opportunities for malicious data exfiltration can also help. Although governance can help to ensure that researchers are trustworthy, malicious attempts to hide data should be considered, for example, in the event of stolen researcher credentials.⁵²

Owing to the different types of data used across the different TREs and the different types of projects it is evident that there is no “one-size-fits-all” solution, but rather a solution needs to be sufficiently flexible to facilitate these differences between projects, data sets, and TREs. Automation can help to address these resource concerns and increase the speed and frequency at which researchers are able to export data. Although human checks are useful, the process has limitations and the risk of human error.⁵³

Typically, the 2 different models for output checking are principle-based and rule-based models. The principle-based model better ensures confidentiality protection and utility of outputs from a statistical perspective, at the expense of being hard to standardise, automate, and verify.⁵⁴

When it comes to the **Safe Settings** principle, TREs should consider the scalability of their infrastructure to support resource-intensive projects in the future. Use of public cloud infrastructure enables much greater flexibility, for a price, and incorporates robust isolation between VMs as standard.⁵⁵

The previously mentioned examples of current practices to detect and prevent instances of unauthorised access, data loss, and researcher misuse should be considered by all TREs to further improve security, where appropriate for the specific TRE infrastructure. Furthermore, TREs must have a **legal agreement** constraining access and use as their data security measure to mitigate the risk of misuse by the researcher. Programs to monitor and record researchers’ behaviour are also useful to reduce misuse.⁵⁶

Some of these security concerns can be mitigated by isolating each project within the TRE to minimize potential damage and limiting the privileges of the researchers in the environment, using virtualisation or containerisation techniques. Similar to the recommendations for data checks, there is a clear need for tools that can support the TRE team in checking the data and code that researchers wish to bring into the environment. Although there are clear concerns about fully automating this process, developing tools to support these checks can significantly speed up the process and assist with the detection of malicious code.⁵⁷

Federated queries enable federated learning that can train ML algorithms from diverse data sets without exchanging data. Federated learning can be effective in diagnosing uncommon diseases, and it can also reinforce data privacy and security if the process of data being stored and processed is supported by privacy-preserving and cryptographic techniques. Furthermore, federated learning complies with data protection regulations including General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). However, federated learning is vulnerable to different attacks such as inference attacks (eg, membership and reconstruction attacks) and poisoning attacks, which can

⁵² Kavianpour et al., 5–6.

⁵³ Kavianpour et al., 6.

⁵⁴ Kavianpour et al., 6.

⁵⁵ Kavianpour et al., 7.

⁵⁶ Kavianpour et al., 8.

⁵⁷ Kavianpour et al., 9.

violate GDPR. The possibility of some of these attacks can be mitigated by the application of privacy-preserving mechanisms including secure multiparty computation, differential privacy, and encrypted transfer learning methods; however, differencing attacks remain difficult to guard against. Supporting federated queries of data from external sources is a feature of interest for the next-generation TREs.⁵⁸

Incorporating a logging and monitoring system into the TRE is important. This system can include log-in attempts, including username, time and date of access, IP address, type of activity conducted during the session (eg, which tools were used, for how long, and any processes that were running), details of any imports and exports (including file name and file size), and access type (successful or denied). Furthermore, having a real-time alert system can warn the TRE team promptly in case of any malicious attempts and assist in preventing unwanted disclosure and blocking access.⁵⁹

In respect of the principle of **Safe Computing**, in comparison with local (“on-premise”) servers, storing data, especially sensitive data (eg, health data), in the public cloud can be considered more secure because of its enhanced security measures and the expert advice available from the cloud service providers. However, most TREs currently use on-premise servers, which simplify data governance and data locality issues and provide consistent performance and predictable costs. It was interesting to see that some TREs plan to switch to public cloud in the future, as the public cloud can scale more easily and provide access to next-generation services such as AI or ML, containers, and so on.⁶⁰

Finally, regarding the **Safe People** principle, the study highlights that training, such as information governance training, is vital to ensure that researchers understand their responsibilities and should be considered by all TREs. Through training, researchers will clearly understand what they are allowed to do with the data. TREs must implement suitable review and management processes to further ensure that researchers are using the TREs appropriately. Best practice approaches to delivering effective training for TRE researchers, which not only support the use of the TRE but also facilitate building shared attitudes and responsibilities in protecting data, are widely available.⁶¹

Recommendations for enhancing existing TREs

The study made the following recommendations for enhancing TRE above and beyond the Five Safes:⁶²

- Improved support for programming capabilities in the environment (eg, Python and R), to advance the analytical capabilities of their TRE and subsequently support large-scale studies
- Support for importing data, algorithms, and code to the environment was frequently described as another high-priority feature

⁵⁸ Kavianpour et al., 9.

⁵⁹ Kavianpour et al., 9.

⁶⁰ Kavianpour et al., 9–10.

⁶¹ Kavianpour et al., 10.

⁶² Kavianpour et al., 10–11.

- Licensing of proprietary software tools presents a further limitation regarding the incorporation of software into the environment, because not all licenses cover use within a TRE
- Support federated learning to advance data movement among TREs, where data sets need to be shared and accessible
- Support for additional data modalities, such as imaging and genomic data, needs to follow a proper risk assessment, and TREs would have to ensure that they liaise with data custodians regarding the specific risks. It was widely acknowledged by the participants that there were many security challenges around allowing researchers to bring their own data and code into the environment, and until solutions to these challenges have been developed, many TREs will be reluctant to support this
- Simplify the process for researchers to access data within their TRE in the future. The process and checks required before researchers are granted access to the data were perceived as cumbersome and slow. Sometimes, this administrative process is further delayed owing to backlog of project review requests, committees being slow to make decisions, ethics board approval, and researchers completing relevant training courses and privacy training.
- Improved governance processes, ie, all data sets in their TRE were treated as high risk and had to go through the same governance process, even though some data sets were actually low risk.
- TREs are considering migrating to a public cloud for improved scalability and flexibility, including GPU access, great on-demand computing power, and reduced management overheads, whereas several TREs have already made this transition
- TRE is looking to enhance their security through improved logging of activities, such as data copying between machines, and better behaviour tracking.
- Concerns about intellectual property when the code was developed within the TRE. The participant acknowledged that researchers may have concerns regarding how the code that they develop or test in a TRE can be accessed by the TRE operators. Policies and practices to govern this should be established to protect both parties. Technical solutions to this problem, such as trusted computing and enclave approaches, can also be explored

Conclusions

TREs are essential for securely managing and analysing sensitive data in healthcare and other sectors. As the demand for more advanced data capabilities grows, TREs must evolve to support next-generation technologies and methodologies. TREs are indispensable for securely managing and analysing sensitive data, particularly in healthcare and other domains. As technological demands evolve, TREs must adapt to support next-generation methodologies, including advanced interoperability and collaboration frameworks. The DARE UK Blueprint, built on the Five Safes framework, provides a technology-agnostic reference for TRE implementation while

aligning with FAIR principles. Although designed within the UK legal context, its mapping to the EOSC-ENTRUST project demonstrates its adaptability to European TRE architectures, such as those in Norway and Finland, where output approval processes differ due to organisational or legal variations.

Despite its robust alignment with existing deployments, gaps remain in addressing certain requirements, including safe user training and certification, data access requests, and pseudonymization. While they are not part of any standard reference architecture for good reasons, these gaps highlight the need for explicit modeling of capabilities in the infrastructure layer to better accommodate diverse TRE needs.

In terms of enabling next-generation capabilities, researchers have pointed at the need for simplifying processes for researchers, fostering collaboration through inter-TRE networking, and adopting innovations like blockchain for enhanced transparency and accountability. Moving forward, TREs must address challenges surrounding intellectual property, federated learning, and risk assessments for diverse modalities. Migration to public cloud infrastructures and improved security measures, such as logging and behaviour tracking, were also recommended for scalability and data protection.

By adopting standardised frameworks, leveraging emerging technologies, and ensuring governance processes remain efficient and adaptable, TREs can transform into hubs for secure and collaborative scientific discovery while maintaining robust protections for sensitive data.

There is also an increasing demand for fostering collaboration among researchers within TREs while maintaining robust security protocols. Inter-TRE networking solutions that allow sharing of insights without compromising confidentiality were identified as potential areas for innovation. Furthermore, the development of standardised frameworks for data interoperability was deemed essential for enhancing the efficiency of cross-TRE studies. To address the growing demand for transparency and accountability, TREs are encouraged to adopt blockchain-based systems for immutable tracking of data usage and research outcomes. These advancements could transform TREs into hubs not only for analysis but also for secure and collaborative scientific discovery.

Finally, TREs can support regulatory bodies by unlocking evidence-based regulatory learnings gathered from the work of researchers and other collaborators in a TRE. When integrated as part of a testing environment in a regulatory sandbox, a TRE could enable data-driven policymaking which is essential for the deployment of any healthcare AI application.

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Bibliography

- EOSC-ENTRUST. 'European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) Project'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://eosc-entrust.eu/about>.
- EOSC-ENTRUST. 'European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) Project'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://eosc-entrust.eu/drivers>.
- 'FinnGen: An Expedition into Genomics and Medicine | FinnGen'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://www.finnngen.fi/en>.
- 'Genomic Medicine Sweden and the Danish National Genome Center Strengthen Collaboration in Personalised Medicine | Genomic Medicine Sweden'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://genomicmedicine.se/en/2024/12/19/gms-and-danish-national-genome-center-strengthen-collaboration-in-precision-medicine/>.
- 'Genomic Medicine Sweden Strategic Plan 2021-2030'. Genomic Medicine Sweden, May 2021. <https://genomicmedicine.se/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/GMS-10-year-strategy.pdf>.
- 'HUNT Cloud'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://about.hdc.ntnu.no/>.
- Kavianpour, Sanaz, James Sutherland, Esma Mansouri-Benssassi, Natalie Coull, and Emily Jefferson. 'Next-Generation Capabilities in Trusted Research Environments: Interview Study'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 24, no. 9 (20 September 2022): e33720. <https://doi.org/10.2196/33720>.
- Njølstad, Pål Rasmus, Ole Andreas Andreassen, Søren Brunak, Anders D. Børglum, Joakim Dillner, Tõnu Esko, Paul W. Franks, et al. 'Roadmap for a Precision-Medicine Initiative in the Nordic Region'. *Nature Genetics* 51, no. 6 (June 2019): 924–30. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-019-0391-1>.
- Nordic Council of Ministers. 'Action Plan for Vision 2030', 14 December 2020. <https://www.norden.org/en/information/action-plan-vision-2030>.
- 'NORTRE'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://nortre.no/>.
- Sætrom, Pål, Heikki Lehtälä, Christine Stansberg, Haneef Awan, and Ahmad Hesam. 'EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year One Version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework', 10 December 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>.
- SciLifeLab. 'National Genomics Infrastructure (NGI)'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://www.scilifelab.se/units/ngi/>.
- 'Services for Sensitive Data (TSD) - University of Oslo'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/index.html>.
- Sheppard, Hadley E. 'Considerations in Establishing Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the Nordics'. *Lifebit* (blog), 30 June 2023. <https://www.lifebit.ai/trusted-research-environment/considerations-in-establishing-trusted-research-environments-in-the-nordics>.
- University of Bergen. 'SAFE'. Accessed 2 March 2025. <https://www.uib.no/en/foremployees/131011/safe>.